

There's an App for That – Helping Prevent Suicide

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INTRODUCTION

United States in 2015, on average, there were 121 suicides every day (CDC, 2017). For age groups 15 to 24 and 25 to 34, suicide is the second leading cause of death; ranked above homicide, heart disease and cancer. In fact, suicide is one of the top ten leading causes of death in ALL age groups, except those under nine and over 65 (id.).

For Christopher Munch, the quest to prevent suicide is personal. As a child, he lost his best friend to suicide. It has been Christopher's vision to develop the first free, publicly available application that allows anyone to complete a suicide risk assessment. That goal has come to fruition in the form of the Suicide Prevention App (SPA).

The Suicide Prevention Application (SPA) launched in September 2016 and the Android version (available via Google Play) launched in August 2017 (the iOS version is in development). To date, there are over six thousand users across the two platforms. The risk assessment that makes up the app is based on protocols that are currently being used by healthcare professionals. At the end of the assessment, a report is downloaded that gives recommendations to the user on what the plan should be. This approach takes the guesswork and any potential bias the user may have out of the equation, thereby facilitating the expediency in which the suicidal person can get the help they need.

AIM

The biggest challenge for SPA is obtaining industry support for this unconventional method of conducting risk assessments. Thus, the overall objective of this research is to validate the SPA protocol to ensure that SPA is on par with or better than the current protocols in use by healthcare professionals. Specifically, SPA is to be evaluated to compare sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive values (PPV), negative predictive values (NPV) and the area under the curve (AUC) (Doran, 2016) to that of four known protocols, namely the Suicide Intent Scale, Beck Depression Inventory – II, SAD PERSONS scale and the Comprehensive Suicide Risk Assessment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This issue will be explored utilizing both qualitative and quantitative field research methodologies. Specifically, SPA will be implemented in an undergraduate college or university. The target audience is students 18 to 24, but all data obtained will be utilized.

The app will be circulated via a general announcement to the student population and posted on the school's student webpage. The instructions for using the app will simply be to fill in the assessment as truthfully and as completely as possible. Participants can choose to use any available operating system to complete the assessment (i.e. web, Android or iOS). If the participant feels they are in an immediate crisis situation, the app contains a one-click mechanism that will immediately put the participant in contact with the national suicide hotline.

In addition to answering the risk-ranked questions, the participants will be required to fill in as much of their demographic information as they are comfortable with divulging. Demographic questions will

include age, ethnicity, gender identification, sexuality, and both home and school postal codes. Data will be collected and analyzed on a weekly basis. The weekly analysis will include both the assessments submitted since the previous week as well as a consolidated analysis of all submitted assessments. The date and time that the participant submitted the assessment will be captured within the metadata so trending on seasonality and other precipitating events can be compared with the increase or decrease in overall assessments submitted and the responses contained within the assessments.

After a set period of time, a follow-up survey will be sent to the student population in the same manner as described for the initial request for participation. The survey will include questions related to the assessment itself from a usability perspective, whether the participant completed any of the recommendations the SPA app suggested, and the participants' overall feelings about their current mental health. The participant will also have the option of including their contact information for additional follow-up questions and/or an in- person interview.

RESULTS

Preliminary data from the initial launch of the Suicide Prevention App is currently being analyzed. Results will be updated as soon as the analysis is complete.

CONCLUSIONS

Conclusions based on data are not yet available. The information will be updated as soon as the analysis is complete.

KEYWORDS

Suicide Prevention, Risk Analysis, At-Risk Persons

BIOGRAPHY

Polly A. College is in the midst of her doctoral thesis at Drexel University's College of Computing and Informatics in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. She is an analyst in the Environment, Health and Safety Department at ADT Security Services and is a consultant to ISD Innovations, Inc., the developer of the Suicide Prevention App. Additionally, Polly serves as a language editor at De Gruyter Open, Ltd.